

The Reading of Others – the Impact of User Tracking on Libraries¹

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Summary

In recent years, the major science publishers have evolved away from publishing content providers to data analytics businesses. As platform companies, they generate high margins and use this capital to buy up alternative offers emerging from the science community and to expand into other business areas. The goal is to make themselves indispensable in all central processes of the research life cycle, so that we should see this as a vendor lock-in, just as it is known from the information sector. To this end, publishers have equipped their platforms with tools for comprehensive user tracking. At the same time, they are trying to bring access authentication under their control in order to ensure personalized access to each user. Some publishers or their parent corporations also intertwine with the security industry and (semi-)government actors in opaque data deals that also bring university networks into view. This essay attempts to analyze this development and outline the consequences.

1. Tracking

Digital media dominate academic libraries, and an end to the growth is hardly in sight, not least in view of the push triggered by the pandemic. The widespread closure of libraries and the conversion to digital teaching have changed information behavior and media practices even in disciplines that were not conspicuous as early adopters in the field. Since a complete reversal, for example in the area of teaching, is not to be expected and library acquisition decisions have also been adapted, this change will be lasting and perpetuated - all the more so as digital media in science integrate themselves into the broad trend of technically assisted reading and writing - from the use of collaborative writing tools to text mining. The digitization of knowledge work requires a new understanding of good scientific practice as a basis, because this changed media practice is exposed to other dependencies than in the past and must therefore be able to rely on honesty in a different way - unfortunately, the opposite is all too often the case.

The fact that assisted reading quickly turns into researched reading has been under discussion for a very long time in the case of e-book readers. Selection of reading, reading time, reading speed, marking of passages - the lack of transparency about what happens with this collected data is only surpassed by the disappearance of some books from the devices of their readers.² Clifford Lynch analyzed this development a few years ago³ and referred in his comments on scientific literature to a blog post by Eric Hellman from 2015, in which this is already a topic.⁴ One must therefore assume

¹ This text is a machine-based translation of the journal article »Das Lesen der Anderen« in order to provide easier access for non-German speaking interested parties, also the German language quotes were therefore transferred. Consider this version a »post-print derivative« and please refer to the original in case of references or citations: Siems, R. (2022). Das Lesen der Anderen: Die Auswirkungen von User Tracking auf Bibliotheken. *O-Bib. Das Offene Bibliotheksjournal / Herausgeber VDB*, 9(1), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.5282/o-bib/5797>

² Cf. Stone, Brad: Amazon erases Orwells Books from Kindle, in: New York Times 17.07.2009. https://www.nytimes.com/2009/07/18/technology/companies/18amazon.html?_r=2

³ Cf. Lynch, Clifford: The Rise of Reading Analytics and the Emerging Calculus of Reader Privacy in the Digital World, *First Monday* 4 (22), 2017. <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v22i4.7414>

⁴ Cf. Hellman, Eric: 16 of the top 20 research journals let ad networks spy on their readers, Go to Hellman 12.03.2015. <https://go-to-hellman.blogspot.com/2015/03/16-of-top-20-research-journals-let-ad.html>

that monitoring the information behavior of scientists and students has probably not been around for less time than an evaluation of private reading in electronic form. For several years, individualized usage profiles of scientific information have been created, the data aggregated, and traded in ways that are still mostly unknown.

In contrast to what is happening with digital media for private end customers, however, the monitoring of information behavior in the scientific field remained rather under the radar for a long time. It was not until the controversy over modified authentication methods for publishing platforms that the relevant contributions by Cody Hanson⁵ that were fundamental to the topic emerged, along with further initiatives from the scientific sector⁶ and an official statement on the part of the Committee for Scientific Libraries and Information Systems (AWBI) of the German Research Foundation (DFG).⁷

The AWBI briefing paper is foundational to the issue: it succinctly explains the current shift among major scholarly publishers⁸ and their move toward a data analytics business, some methods of data collection, and draws an initial conclusion that calls for a broad discourse on the potential legal violations of tracking and the dangers to researchers. The presentation of tracking methods given here is based on presentations at the »Bibliothekartag« Bremen 2021,⁹ and follows on from the information paper and attempts to add further points.¹⁰

1.1. First Party Data

So-called first party data is the data from the first hand: login data, e-mail distribution lists for newsletters and author directories would be examples from the area of information supply. This kind of data is particularly valuable from the point of view of data analytics because it is real data from real people and not just - as with some tracking methods - merely calculated allocations. Accordingly, there is an intense effort on the commercial Internet to gain access to this kind of data. This can be, for example, identification numbers of devices or, on websites, features such as »Remember me on this device« or »Login with...«. The goal is always clear identification at the beginning, so that from there the online biography of the person in question can be tracked without interruption and synchronized with further information.

This intention must also be assumed to be behind the efforts of publishers to gain access to user authentication through technical changes. The Resource Access (RA21), Seamless Access and Get Full Text Research (GetFTR) initiatives presented by the publishers have in common that they are based on SAML technology¹¹ like the common Shibboleth application. However, they are integrating this into their platforms to a much greater extent than before and are thus increasingly influencing the question of which data is transmitted for authentication or not. A joint statement

⁵ See Hanson, Cody: User Tracking on Academic Publisher Platforms, <https://www.codyh.com/writing/tracking.html> and the recorded lecture linked there.

⁶ See SPARC: Addressing the Alarming Systems of Surveillance Systems built by Library Vendors, <https://sparcopen.org/news/2021/addressing-the-alarming-systems-of-surveillance-built-by-library-vendors/> and the call carried by the Information Centre for Life Sciences ZBMed »Stop Tracking Science!«, <https://stoptrackingscience.eu/>. There you will also find a wealth of further literature on the subject.

⁷ Cf. DFG: Data tracking in research: aggregation and use or sale of usage data by academic publishers, https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/programme/lis/datentracking_papier_en.pdf

⁸ For more details, see SPARC: Landscape Analysis, 29.03.2019, <https://infrastructure.sparcopen.org/landscape-analysis> and the updates: <https://sparcopen.org/news/2020/sparc-releases-update-to-landscape-analysis-and-accompanying-interactive-website/>

⁹ Cf. <https://bibliothekartag2021.de/>

¹⁰ For a focused overview presentation of web tracking as a whole, see Reuben Binns: Tracking on the Web, Mobiles and Internet-of-Things, arXiv 26.01.2022, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2201.10831>

¹¹ Security Assertion Markup Language, a standard for exchanging authentication data.

by DBV and the Alliance of German Science Organizations therefore came to a clear conclusion regarding RA21:

„These advantages are potentially offset by the danger that, as part of the further development of SSO [Single Sign On; author's note], providers will stipulate the transfer of personal information by the institutional identity provider beyond what is necessary as a precondition for use. Also, in order not to disadvantage institutions that do not operate their own identity provider, an exclusive specification of SSO-based procedures is not desirable from the point of view of the information infrastructure institutions. In principle, IP-based access control should always be offered as an alternative. When implementing web-based SSO procedures, it must be ensured that data protection is also fully implemented in accordance with the principle of data economy (privacy by design).“¹²

Publishers continue to pursue their strategy unimpressed and using questionable methods: for example, the American Chemical Society set opt-out deadlines for U.S. libraries to switch to Seamless Access in the middle of the first Corona lockdown.¹³ In Germany, Seamless Access has not yet played a role, although publishers are increasingly offering Google CASA (Campus Activated Subscriber Access). As part of the "Google Scholar Subscriber Links" program, Google CASA enables Google to remember access rights for on-campus searches via Google Scholar and existing logins to the Google account, and then enables access off-campus as well, bypassing the otherwise necessary remote access systems.¹⁴ What is stored where and for how long is just as unclear as who sees all the data. Since a number of publishers use the service, it is conceivable that they could obtain information about usage patterns of individuals across publishers in this way.

Complementing such efforts of collecting first party data is the embedding of a hash in the metadata of an article PDF that changes with each download. In conjunction with the timestamp of the download, this makes each PDF individualizable. This not only captures login data and information behavior, but potentially also the distribution of documents, e.g., through author sharing.¹⁵

1.2. Third Party Data

Third party data is understood to mean that not only is the company's own, self-collected data evaluated, but an external third party analyzes it together with data from other sources. Google CASA thus forms a link between first and third party data, since it provides direct identification as in the case of authentication, but actually belongs to the services of third parties. These third parties with their integrated data analytics are the common revenue model on the commercial Internet. Whenever a cookie banner pops up on a web page (and often enough when it doesn't), tracking

¹² Empfehlungen zu Methoden zur Kontrolle des Zugriffs auf wissenschaftliche Informationsressourcen. Ein gemeinsames Papier von Deutscher Bibliotheksverband e.V. (dbv) und Schwerpunktinitiative Digitale Information der Allianz der deutschen Wissenschaftsorganisationen, 27.11.2019, https://dbv-cs.e-fork.net/sites/default/files/2020-11/2019_11_27_dbv_Stellungnahme_Empfehlungen%20zu%20Methoden%20zur%20Kontrolle%20des%20Zugriffs%20auf%20wissenschaftliche%20Informationsressourcen.pdf. See also McLean, Jaclyn; Stregger, Elizabeth: Sounding the Alarm. Scholarly Information and Global Information Companies in 2021, in: Partnership. The Canadian Journal of Library and Information Practice and Research 2 (16), 2021, S. 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.21083/partnership.v16i2.6692>

¹³ Cf. Hanson, Cody: E-resource librarians, Twitter, @codyh, 26.03.2020, <https://twitter.com/codyh/status/1243250490403483648>

¹⁴ Cf. Vogel, Christian: Kennen Sie Google CASA? medinfo. Informationen aus Medizin, Bibliothek und Fachpresse, 08.07.2020, <https://www.medinfo-agmb.de/archives/2020/07/08/6880>

¹⁵ Cf. Saunders, Jonny: More fun publisher surveillance, Twitter, @json_dirs, 26.01.2022, https://twitter.com/json_dirs/status/1486120144141123584 and Wjst, Matthias: Personalized PDFs. Science Surf 22.01.2022, <https://www.wjst.de/blog/sciencesurf/2022/01/personalized-pdfs/>

through the arsenal of Advertising Technology (AdTech) is in play. The aim is always to be able to track the continuous history of online behavior of individualized persons, either to market aggregated information behavior profiles or to influence behavioral decisions through manipulative user guidance (nudging).¹⁶ On the major publishing platforms, Cody Hanson was able to prove 139 such third parties. He explains their problem:

„The reason I was interested in third-party assets being loaded on these sites is that any JavaScript loaded on these pages has access to the entire DOM, or document object model, meaning it can read the address and contents of the page. It also has access to every user action that happens on that page, and can itself load additional scripts from additional sources. So when, for example, a publisher puts JavaScript from Google on its pages, Google can record any information from the page about the article being sought, or search terms from a library user in the publisher platform. Fourteen of the fifteen publisher platforms included Google code on the article page.“¹⁷

In addition to the major companies in the tracking business such as Google and Facebook, there are a number of other trackers as well as »meta-trackers« in the form of data-aggregating audience tools for target group analysis from Adobe, Neustar, Oracle, AddThis, etc., which combine data from many sources and thus classify the tracked persons into characteristic groups (age, gender, interests, sexual orientation, income, etc.). In addition, there are so-called finger printers or canvas printers such as Double Click, which identify people based on their device traces, even though they try to avoid this through their browser settings. Since audience tools, for example, work together with a large number of other data brokers, the data collected in this way flows into entire ecosystems of data utilization, as Wolfie Christl visualizes using the example of the marketing service provider Acxiom/liveramp:¹⁸

© Cracked Labs CC BY-SA 4.0, April/May 2017. Disclaimer: the mentioned companies typically keep information about their activities secret. This illustration is based on publicly available information, mainly the companies' own statements. Every effort has been made to accurately interpret and represent the companies' activities, but we cannot accept any liability in the case of eventual errors. Sources: Acxiom website, press releases, brochures, annual reports, and response to US congress inquiry. Liveramp website, brochures, press releases, presentations. Ibotta website, Crossix website, press releases. FreckleIoT press releases. For details about the sources see the report "Corporate Surveillance in Everyday Life".

Fig. 1: Data flows Acxiom (CC-BY-SA 4.0 Wolfie Christl)

¹⁶ For the development of this problem cf. Crain, Matthew: Profit over Privacy. How Surveillance Advertising Conquered the Internet. Minneapolis 2021

¹⁷ Hanson, Cody; see footnote 5.

¹⁸ Cf. Christl, Wolfie: Corporate Surveillance in Everyday Life. How Companies Collect, Combine, Analyze, Trade, and Use Personal Data on Billions. Wien 2017, S. 55. <https://crackedlabs.org/en/corporate-surveillance>

Axiom/liveramp can be traced on the Nature website. Due to this collaboration of publishers with AdTech, the previously rather protected »special biotope« of the scientific information world has thus been dissolved. What a scientist researches combines in an unbroken online (and partly offline) biography with browsing the online store, the Twitter timeline, the preferred newspapers, the information whether one has children, the jogging route and the purchases in the supermarket around the corner.

1.3. Bidstream and Portscanning

The business of third parties has long been criticized as surveillance advertising. Major internet companies are slowly distancing themselves, and the EU's Digital Services Act is also undertaking initial, albeit inadequate, regulation.¹⁹ However, developments are mixed: In response to economic pressure, regulations on Personal Information Management Services (PIMS) were included in Section 26 of the Telecommunications Telemedia Data Protection Act (TTDSG) in Germany, which, due to the inadequate system, ultimately threatens to turn third party data into first party data by allowing consent to be given »in advance« after logging on to a central website so that cookie banners can be omitted afterwards. This will give back to the ad tech industry the leeway that browser, device, and service providers are currently taking away from it.²⁰

PIMS could, if modeled appropriately, help to efficiently design data protection improvements for users, but the current status is criticized in the expert discussion as „regulating past the problem“.²¹ The increasing reliance on first-party data, which motivates the activities for authentication and the establishment of Google CASA on the part of publishers, is accordingly also a goal of the ad tech industry:

„Leaving the cookie behind means that brands and publishers will have more accurate data that they collect from known individuals, but it will be a smaller footprint because it misses the many visitors that never log-in or opt-in. Perhaps 20% of users are logged in on a site, and so audience addressability from the buyer's perspective would be insufficient without data sharing between publishers, or without the help of sophisticated, scaled third parties offering probabilistic modeling. Getting confidence in this modeling, is an exercise in 'degrees of determinism'. Everyone benefits if buyers can gain confidence that they are trading on real, good data.“²²

Internationally, the industry is also moving towards technologies such as bid streaming, which has been around for a long time. Real time bidding allows automated, real-time bidding for advertising space on the Internet. It is the technological basis behind what is shaping our Internet experience as »Programmatic Advertising«: the »random« matching of advertising banners to what we are doing on the web. Our interactions, such as search queries, are auctioned off in real time to play ads tailored to the individual in milliseconds. What originally emerged in the context of Google Adwords can also transmit a variety of data about a person, their device, and their location without

¹⁹ Cf. Röttger, Tania: Auf dem Weg zum Digital Services Act. Wie die EU Gesetze gegen Desinformation macht, Correctiv 26.03.2021, <https://correctiv.org/faktencheck/hintergrund/2021/03/26/auf-dem-weg-zum-digital-services-act-wie-die-eu-gesetze-gegen-desinformation-macht/>

²⁰ Engeler, Malte: Das neue Telekommunikation-Telemedien-Datenschutzgesetz. Was es über das regulatorische Klima der deutschen Datenschutzpolitik verrät, Telemedicus 14.07.2021, <https://www.telemedicus.info/soko21-das-neue-telekommunikation-telemedien-datenschutzgesetz-was-es-ueber-das-regulatorische-klima-der-deutschen-datenschutzpolitik-verraet/>

²¹ See the talk of Louisa Specht-Riemenschneider on the »Datentag« 03.11.2021; <https://stiftungdatenschutz.org/veranstaltungen/unsere-veranstaltungen-detailansicht/ttdsg-einwilligungsverwaltung-234#lg=1&slide=6>

²² Baron, Andrew: Identity Innovations Will Create Complexity, Shared Standards Can Help, Pubmatic 08.05.2020, <https://pubmatic.com/blog/identity-innovations-will-create-complexity-shared-standards-can-help/>

cookies by linking to an identifier.²³ Evidence of this is also emerging on publishing platforms. Real Time Bidding is currently the subject of a lawsuit at the Hamburg Regional Court.²⁴

Portscanning, i.e., searching for open ports of a computer (system), is a technology on the edge of legality according to German legal understanding if it is directed at other people's computers and networks. Searching for open ports can be seen as a precursor to the acts sanctioned in the German »hacker paragraphs« 202c and 303b StGB. Nevertheless, portscanning is used internationally in the field of risk solutions, i.e., the industry dedicated to fraud prevention, among other things, but also precisely with in-depth data analysis predictive analytics, »prediction products«, developed and sold to the security industry for Big Data policing (see Section 4.3.). Some time ago, for example, it became public that eBay also uses portscanning of site visitors in a bundle of measures.²⁵ ThreatMetrix, a company that claims to be able to identify 4.5 billion devices and belongs to the Elsevier parent company RELX, is often used here. Wolfie Christl considers ThreatMetrix to be a „global mass surveillance system“ that processes data from 1.4 billion people from 185 countries, and was also able to demonstrate its use on the Elsevier platform ScienceDirect.²⁶ Another company known in the library space that offers risk solutions is Clarivate.

Since the RELX Group also offers data products for government agencies and the security industry, this raises the question of whether such data collections are also processed within the Group for corresponding products such as LexisNexis Risk Solutions. For lack of transparency, not much can be said about this yet (cf. Section 5.3.).

2. Workbenches

„Workflow is the new content“²⁷ - a slogan that actually describes the development in information infrastructures well. The path dependency,²⁸ which can be observed in the supply of information and makes alternatives difficult to develop,²⁹ has filled the publishers' war chests in recent years with profit margins of well over 30 %³⁰ in some cases for a large number of company takeovers - not only, but also with providers in the science sector. Just as the large platforms use strategic acquisitions both to expand their own business field and generally to prevent competition from

²³ Cf. the illustration on slide 45 in Ryan, Johnny: Briefing on adtech, RTB, and the GDPR at dmexco Brave Event, 16.09.2019, <https://de.slideshare.net/JohnnyRyan/briefing-on-adtech-rtb-and-the-gdpr-at-dmexco-brave-event>, and for more details: <https://brave.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/3-bid-request-examples.pdf> (I thank Matthias Eberl for the reference).

²⁴ Cf. Statement of Claim Dr. Johnny Ryan (Plaintiff) v. IAB Technology Laboratory, Inc. (Defendant), Mar. 24, 2021. <https://www.iccl.ie/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/GERMAN-LANGUAGE-ORIGINAL-Schriftsatz-an-das-Landgericht-Hamburg.pdf>

²⁵ Cf. Nemec, Dan: Ebay is port scanning visitors to their website. And they aren't the only ones, nem.ec 24.05.2020, <https://blog.nem.ec/2020/05/24/ebay-port-scanning/>

²⁶ Cf. presentation and screenshots at Christl, Wolfie: ThreatMetrix, Twitter, @WolfieChristl, Jul. 23-Aug. 18, 2020, <https://twitter.com/wolfiechristl/status/1286341387718397952>

²⁷ Dempsey, Lorcan: Workflow is the new content ..., Twitter, @lorcanD, 17.05.2021, <https://twitter.com/lorcand/status/1394276710519087104>

²⁸ Term from organizational psychology that describes the development of an increasing narrowing of the initially diverse options for action to a very narrow »path« that makes a reversal or breakout almost impossible. A classic example is writing keyboards: There are layouts with which one can write up to 30% faster, but the sheer quantity of existing devices and typists trained on the current layout makes a change almost impossible.

²⁹ Cf. Brembs, Björn et al.: Replacing academic journals, Zenodo 24.09.2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5564003>

³⁰ Cf. SPARC 2019, p. 11

developing with them, the large publishers now cover the entire research life cycle through acquisitions.³¹

What Roger Schonfeld discussed in relation only to publishing as an emerging supercontinent,³² is being realized a few years later as an ecosystem that spans all stages of the research process from information research, lab work, writing, publishing, scholarly communication, and metrics production in networked workbenches, and which individual researchers per se no longer even need to leave - and certainly should not. As always in an attention economy, a longer stay means that more data traces are created, so there is more to observe and exploit. Claudio Aspesi calls this „the next battleground“ with an urgent need for action:

„If it doesn't invest in alternative solutions, the academic community may find itself beholden to a small number of vendors for managing communities, data flows, research assessment, and learned society communications, all within digital silos that could hinder the growth of cross-disciplinary collaboration and discovery.“³³

This is what RfII (Council for Information Infrastructures) Chair Petra Gehring called a „live trap for researchers“: „Big players deliberately attack the integrity of scientific exchange. They regard the entire intellectual cycle of state-supported and thus free research as their future product.“³⁴

3. Library Management Systems

Commercial products in the field of library management software are increasingly becoming part of such ecosystems. From the point of view of data analytics, library systems are highly interesting objects because they also contain real data from real people - namely individualized personal data of all users, combined with their media usage behavior, including the part that cannot be measured externally (lending), as well as the financing flows of the library based on this data. Accordingly, all major providers have developed models of library analytics and converted their systems to cloud operation, so that structurally there can no longer be a conclusive overview of the data flows for the users. In addition to researchers, students increasingly come into view as a target here when looking at what OCLC is gathering as a user story for their WorldShare Management Services (WMS) system from the University of Gloucestershire - campus leaders are certainly excited:

„The implementation of WMS at University of Gloucestershire provided a great opportunity to build learning analytics capabilities into a library management system from the ground up. The project has analyzed user transactions involving both print and electronic resources datasets from WMS's circulation data and EZproxy's detailed usage logs. Integrating the data feed with the university's student record system opens further insights. [...] With the user ID, we can now link to the student's course and department [...]. So, we can see how many students in a certain course accessed ScienceDirect, for example. The student record data that we hold is quite comprehensive, so we can even start to compare library resource usage across demographic groups.“³⁵

³¹ Cf. the illustration at <https://stoptrackingscience.eu/background-information/> and the article of Posada, Alejandro; Chen, George: Inequality in Knowledge Production. The integration of Academic Infrastructure by Big Publishers, ELPUB 2018, [10.4000/proceedings.elpub.2018.30](https://doi.org/10.4000/proceedings.elpub.2018.30)

³² Cf. Schonfeld, Roger C.: The Supercontinent of Scholarly Publishing?, The Scholarly Kitchen 03.05.2018, <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2018/05/03/supercontinent-scholarly-publishing/>

³³ Aspesi, Claudio; Brand, Amy: In pursuit of open science, open access is not enough, Science 368, 2020, <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.aba3763>

³⁴ Gehring, Petra: Das Schicksal von Open Science steht auf dem Spiel, Forschung & Lehre 02.08.2021, <https://www.forschung-und-lehre.de/politik/das-schicksal-von-open-science-steht-auf-dem-spiel-3902>

³⁵ Find out which library resources have the greatest influence, <https://www.oclc.org/en/member-stories/gloucestershire.html>. For ExLibris Alma see Sarah Lamdan: Libraries are part of the ed tech surveillance

Such analytics are likely to provide material for student predictive analytics, which is being considered internationally by universities for financial reasons and opens up every possibility of discrimination.³⁶ This is also likely to arouse interest outside the campus, because much „more precisely and comprehensively than a report card or ECTS points, our data profiles provide information about what we know (expertise), how well and how quickly we learn (talent), how we solve situations (competence), how often we try something (frustration tolerance), or whether we dare to take unusual approaches (creativity).“³⁷ At least potential employers, insurance companies, and credit rating agencies will therefore try to gain access as soon as such data are available.

When looking at library systems in this regard, it has long been noted that not only researchers and students, but also libraries and their employees themselves are targets of data-driven exploitation and expropriation:

„Libraries find themselves increasingly dependent on library-providing systems such as Alma, Exlibris, or OCLC, with the consequence that they will later have to buy back their own catalog data. They have licensed the raw data themselves, but the terms on which it is licensed indicate that preparations are underway on the part of the relevant publishers to get control of this strategic asset. What this means for future scholarship and for copyright law is uncertain.“³⁸

Those familiar with the tough business of metadata delivery from library practice see the pattern here of how library workers, especially in the notorious cases as clickworkers like Amazon's Mechanical Turk,³⁹ create and fix data so that it is at all system-ready and usable - apparently only for libraries to then lose their rights to it in the same way that authors do in the traditional publishing model.

Publishers, for their part, have also found interest in library systems for their own purposes. Within a webinar hosted by the Scholarly Network Security Initiative (SNSI),⁴⁰ which is sponsored by a number of publishers, a presentation considered how library software could be used to support the fight against shadow libraries. A proxy plugin for a »Modern Library Architecture« should make a whole range of data accessible: Timestamps, detailed browser information, username, account information, IP address, URLs accessed, device information, location data, user behavior (if the person is accessing different resources than their subject affiliation would suggest), and biometric data. The latter is central and refers to the individual way a user interacts with their device: Typing speed, type of mouse use or touch control - all this adds up to an individual fingerprint with which a university member can be recognized as a SciHub user, even if he or she thinks they have taken

ecosystem, Twitter, @greenarchives1, 02.06.2021,

<https://twitter.com/greenarchives1/status/1400067993929912326>, for EBSCO see: The Evolving Landscape of Library Data Analytics, <https://www.ebsco.com/blogs/ebscopost/evolving-landscape-library-data-analytics>

³⁶ Cf. Shea Swauger: The next normal: Algorithms will take over college, from admissions to advising. The Washington Post 12.11.2021, https://www.washingtonpost.com/outlook/next-normal-algorithms-college/2021/11/12/366fe8dc-4264-11ec-a3aa-0255edc02eb7_story.html

³⁷ Lentsch, Justus: Unsere Bildungsdaten gehören uns! Wiarda Blog 16.02.2021,

<https://www.jmwiarda.de/2021/02/16/unsere-bildungsdaten-geh%C3%B6ren-uns/>

³⁸ Weingart, Peter; Taubert, Niels (Hrsg.): Wissenschaftliches Publizieren. Zwischen Digitalisierung, Leistungsmessung, Ökonomisierung und medialer Beobachtung. Berlin 2016, S. 109.

https://edoc.bbaw.de/files/2662/00_FB38_WissenschaftlichesPublizieren_gesamt_edoc.pdf

³⁹ Amazon's »Mechanical Turk« (named after the historic »Chess Turk«) is a service where clients can digitally post tasks that cannot yet be fully automated, which are then distributed in small packages to be worked on by freelance crowdworkers. As the »last mile of automation«, these programs are currently much in demand for such tasks as improving AI object recognition or audio transcription, doing text proofreading, flagging problematic content on social media, etc. Similar to Uber and other platforms, this type of »microwork« then often involves wage dumping, obstruction of unionization, and permanent overwork, see Gray, Mary L., Suri, Siddharth: Ghost Work. How to Stop Silicon Valley from Building a New Global Underclass. Boston 2019

⁴⁰ <https://www.snsi.info/>

technical security precautions. In order to motivate libraries to install such an „analysis engine“, they should be offered discounts - although such interventions in university network security are likely to meet with reservations on the part of the local data centers. These considerations attracted some public attention,⁴¹ because even if they were presented as hypothetical, they did open up an insight into mentalities. Publishers and system providers seem to be in agreement on this, as at a later SNSI webinar, Don Hamparian of OCLC presented »Libraries as Security Advocates« who naturally protected »publisher assets.«⁴²

4. Business Models

4.1. Open Access

Open access is not a tracking business model, but conversely, one will have to admit that open access does not help against tracking either - at least as long as the publication infrastructures remain what they are and only the direction of money is reversed to charge for publishing instead of reading. A login is not at all necessary for most tracking technologies, which is why Cody Hanson was able to examine an example from PLoS One. As long as traffic is happening on publishing platforms, it can be monitored, analyzed, and monetized. It can be assumed that there will be even greater motivation for tracking when the transition to commercial open access takes place: This is because the transformation is developing a new lack of clarity with regard to usage compared to before, where clearly defined target groups gathered behind uniform authentication systems. This creates a new form of double dipping:⁴³ authors pay with Article Processing Charges (APC), readers with personal data - another variant of volume optimization of revenue, just as the APC-based transformation as a whole, viewed over a longer period of time, is already proving to be significantly more costly.⁴⁴

Most importantly, it should be noted that APC-driven open access in particular helps major publishers establish the workbenches outlined above throughout the research life cycle. Aspesi points out that in the past, in addition to technical and financial limitations, it was copyright that hindered the establishment of truly large multifunctional portals because it legally parceled out content. This obstacle, as Schonfeld also explains in his account of the takeover of ProQuest by Clarivate,⁴⁵ is increasingly falling away with the transformation in the same way that technical progress is also reducing the financial obstacles. The report given by Hubertus Neuhausen of APE2020 shows the state of the discussion, in which the publishers show quite openly how they want to dominate the research cycle in its entirety and cooperate with each other in doing so. The

⁴¹ Cf. Dobusch, Leonhard: News from Elsevier. No open access deal, but spyware against shadow libraries? <https://netzpolitik.org/2020/news-from-elsevier-no-open-access-deal-but-spyware-against-shadow-libraries/>, Metha, Gautama: Proposal to install spyware in university libraries to protect copyrights shocks academics, Coda 13.11.2020, <https://www.codastory.com/authoritarian-tech/spyware-in-libraries/>, the recording of the webinar on Vimeo: <https://vimeo.com/623425480> (from approx. min. 27) and Saunders, Johnny: like the cartel they are, Twitter, @json_dirs, 14.12.2021, https://twitter.com/json_dirs/status/1470633210581192705

⁴² Cf. the recording of the webinar on Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HEBQyg_ezHI (from min. 24:45).

⁴³ Term for the double billing of services, such as in hybrid open access journals, where individual articles are openly accessible after payment of publication fees, but the journal as a whole continues to be offered under the license model.

⁴⁴ Cf. Morrison, Heather et.al.: Open access article processing charges 2011–2021, Sustaining the Knowledge Commons 24.06.2021, <https://sustainingknowledgecommons.org/2021/06/24/open-access-article-processing-charges-2011-2021/>

⁴⁵ Cf. Schonfeld, Roger C.: The New Clarivate Science. A Second-Order Consequence of Open Access, The Scholarly Kitchen 9.12.2021, <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2021/12/09/new-clarivate-science/>

self-critical questions he poses there are very much worth re-reading⁴⁶ - all the more so now that the first »multi-publisher pool« is online.⁴⁷

4.2. People Analytics in Science

The digitalization push in the world of work triggered by the pandemic quickly brought to light a large number of anecdotal reports about control requests from employers. Wolfie Christl has recently presented a detailed study on this subject, which analyzes the development of recent years:⁴⁸ Prepared IT workplaces, sensors in work clothing, evaluation of cash register data, tracking systems for recording the movement patterns of employees both indoors and outdoors, software for process mining of work processes both for their optimization and for identifying »undesirable activities« - all this is shaping the everyday working lives of more and more people. This not only applies to work in production or to mobile caregivers whose minute quotas do not change due to the respective traffic situation and whether the person being cared for is currently having a good or rather bad day - in the development of knowledge work, this has already caused changes and conflicts on campus in the past.⁴⁹

The workbenches described in Section 3. now have the potential to enable people analytics of science. The overarching pieces in particular, such as research information systems, are explicitly advertised as enabling »deeper insights«, and library systems are becoming, as Schonfeld put it in his commentary on Clarivate's buyout of ProQuest, „a component in a larger suite.“⁵⁰ Developments are also being driven by tying deals, as in the Netherlands, where Elsevier was able to secure a contract that enabled open-access publishing for scholars at no additional cost to their previous subscription expenses - if, in return, universities cooperated on »metadata projects« and licensed Elsevier's research information systems.⁵¹ This is a replay of the browser wars of the 1990s, when Microsoft drove Netscape out of the market by tightly coupling Internet Explorer with Windows - because, after all, it will be immediately clear to all scientists that their research output will only be fully recorded in the evaluation instruments and »count« if it has appeared in the publication platform of the same provider. Thus, the market for research information will rapidly clean up and another step into vendor lock-in has been taken.

Anyone who has followed the debates about #IchbinHanna,⁵² can therefore certainly come to the conclusion that there is still room for improvement here: once these workbenches have been consistently coupled and networked, these ecosystems will, on the one hand, form a vendor lock-in for the universities far beyond the area of literature supply, where this constraint already exists. On the other hand, it will then be possible, at least in technical terms, to treat academics in a similar

⁴⁶ Cf. Neuhausen, Hubertus: Open Access? – Ist durch! Aber was ist mit den Daten? ABI Technik 40 (3), 2020, S. 277–291. Online: <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/abitech-2020-2022/html>

⁴⁷ Cf. Lisa Janicke Hinchliffe: Elsevier's ScienceDirect as Content Supercontinent?, The Scholarly Kitchen 10.01.2022, Online: <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2022/01/18/sciencedirect-as-content-supercontinent/>

⁴⁸ Cf. Christl, Wolfie: Digitale Überwachung und Kontrolle am Arbeitsplatz. Von der Ausweitung betrieblicher Datenerfassung zum algorithmischen Management? Wien 2021. Online: <https://crackedlabs.org/daten-arbeitsplatz/info>

⁴⁹ Cf. Siems, Renke: Unser industrielles Erbe. Bibliotheken und die digitale Transformation, in: o-bib 4 (3), 2017. <https://doi.org/10.5282/o-bib/2017H3S1-15>

⁵⁰ Schonfeld, Roger C.: Clarivate to acquire ProQuest, The Scholarly Kitchen 18.05.2021, <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2021/05/18/clarivate-to-acquire-proquest/>

⁵¹ Cf. Knecht, Sicco de: Leaked document on Elsevier negotiations sparks controversy, ScienceGuide 06.11.2019, <https://www.scienceguide.nl/2019/11/leaked-document-on-elsevier-negotiations-sparks-controversy/>

⁵² Under this hashtag, the broad protest movement in Germany against the crushing dependence of many scientists organized against the system of very short fixed-term employment contracts. Cf. the documentation at <https://ichbinhanna.wordpress.com/> and Amrei Bahr et.al.: #IchBinHanna. Prekäre Wissenschaft in Deutschland. Frankfurt/M. 2022

way to the »picker« in the Amazon warehouse with its close-meshed monitoring. There will be no need to be as heavy-handed as recently at the University of Liverpool, where the less cited scientists were simply dismissed to cover a financial hole.⁵³

All of these developments echo a small half-sentence from Christl's study: „Employee data become a product.“⁵⁴ Employees generally gain nothing from this, but even otherwise the benefits of the product do not necessarily materialize where some imagine. Ireland's Science Foundation, for example, had recently decided to drive its strategic realignment in a data-based way, and chose Elsevier as its partner to do so:

„They have access to a vast array of data, and this will help us to establish where Ireland is good and nearly good in emergent and convergent technologies. It will also help us decide on the actions we need to take to make us really good. For example, we might see a certain field where we are nearly good at present and find that we need to recruit top talent or run new funding calls to support it.“⁵⁵

Where this miraculous treasure trove of data comes from was apparently not questioned. But it must be said: User tracking has begun to intervene in scientific competition.

4.3. Risk Solutions

The science sector is not the only area that the major publishers or their parent companies and trusted service providers are turning to with a data analytics business model. As mentioned, more and more players are becoming active in the »risk solutions« area such as big data policing. In the latter, Elsevier parent company RELX and Thomson Reuters have been active for several years. With their LexisNexis Risk Solutions and Clear products, they offer aggregated data products for the security industry. These activities go back a long way: in 2006, RELX was one of the early investors in the data analytics firm Palantir,⁵⁶ which was founded by Peter Thiel with funds from In-Q-Tel, the venture capital arm of the CIA, among others, and has since served a clientele of military and intelligence agencies, as well as financial services.⁵⁷ Since 2010, Thomson Reuters has also partnered with Palantir.⁵⁸

Risk solutions are apparently a booming business: in 2020, Thomson Reuters had contracts worth over \$60 million with the militarized border police ICE (Immigrants and Customs Enforcement)

⁵³ Cf. Bishop, Dorothy: University staff cuts under the cover of a pandemic. The cases of Liverpool and Leicester, BishopBlog 03.03.2021, <http://deevybee.blogspot.com/2021/03/university-staff-cuts-under-cover-of.html> – after protests, the cuts were largely withdrawn, cf.: University of Liverpool staff call off strike action, BBC News 01.10.2021, <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-england-merseyside-58766202>

⁵⁴ Christl 2021, p. 11

⁵⁵ McCall, Barry: Propelling Ireland to first-mover status in research and innovation, in: The Irish Times 26.08.2021, <https://www.irishtimes.com/sponsored/innovation-partner-profiles/propelling-ireland-to-first-mover-status-in-research-and-innovation-1.4655112>

⁵⁶ See the own statement: Investing in disruptive data & analytics technologies, <https://www.relx.com/our-business/our-stories/rev-venture-partners>

⁵⁷ Cf.: A (Pretty) Complete History of Palantir, Social Calculations 11.08.2015, <https://web.archive.org/web/20190724214959/http://www.socialcalculations.com/2015/08/a-pretty-complete-history-of-palantir.html>

⁵⁸ Cf.: Thomson Reuters and Palantir Technologies Enter Exclusive Agreement to Create Next-Generation Analytics Platform for Financial Clients, MarketWired 12.04.2010, <https://web.archive.org/web/20180708032604/http://m.marketwired.com/press-release/thomson-reuters-palantir-technologies-enter-exclusive-agreement-create-next-generation-nyse-tri-1167653.htm>

alone,⁵⁹ LexisNexis concluded a contract with ICE for \$16.8 million in the spring of 2021.⁶⁰ The data products aggregate data from many different public and private sources with information such as that collected by Schufa in Germany, but also with databases of car license plates and customers of mobile phone networks. ThreatMetrix, mentioned in section 2.3, is part of LexisNexis Risk Solutions. ICE's use of these databases serves, among other things, to prepare raids to locate and deport immigrants - which civil rights organizations say are ongoing human rights violations.⁶¹ U.S. policymakers also sometimes view the use of these products as an abuse of rights.⁶²

Thomson Reuters and LexisNexis are now simultaneously the authoritative providers of specialized legal information in the United States; it is impossible to work without Westlaw and LexisNexis. Accordingly, the nightmare that activists like law professor Sarah Lamdan⁶³ pursue would be that lawyers contribute to the capture of their clients through research in specialized databases - which the firms in question deny, of course.⁶⁴ Nonetheless, the revenues from the academic sector help to further expand such activities. And since the data is collected globally, as it is by ThreatMetrix, and the data products are likewise sold globally, undocumented immigrants need not be the only and last people against whom it is used.

The American librarian Shea Swauger dealt with Thomson Reuters Clear in a self-experiment until he had his file (that's what you have to call it) in his hands. On 41 pages, his personal and family circumstances were recorded, when he lived where, real estate ownership, when he bought a used car from whom, voter turnout and political preference, financial situation - and a lot of incorrect information was included. But correcting them or deleting the data was not at all possible:

„To wrap it up, @Westlaw, through CLEAR, collects a shit ton of data about you. They share it with law enforcement, including @ICEgov, and anyone who has enough money to buy CLEAR. And for most people, there's nothing you can do about it[.]“⁶⁵

Meanwhile, there is also an opposite development in this area: not only are information service providers pushing into the security industry, but the whole thing is also happening the other way around: Palantir is using the pandemic to penetrate the research data business with sometimes rude methods and to devote itself to the lucrative market of health data.⁶⁶

⁵⁹ Cf. Lyons, Kim: Thomson Reuters faces pressure over ICE contracts, The Verge 21.05.2020, <https://www.theverge.com/2020/5/21/21266431/thomson-reuters-ice-clear-software>

⁶⁰ Cf. Biddle, Sam: LexisNexis to Provide Giant Database of Personal Information to ICE, The Intercept 02.04.2021, <https://theintercept.com/2021/04/02/ice-database-surveillance-lexisnexis/>

⁶¹ See the webpage »No Tech for ICE«, <https://notechforice.com/>

⁶² Cf.: House Committee of Oversight and Reform: Oversight Subcommittee Launches Investigation into Sale of Utility Customer Info to ICE for Deporting Immigrants, Press Release 26.02.2021, <https://oversight.house.gov/news/press-releases/oversight-subcommittee-launches-investigation-into-sale-of-utility-customer-info>

⁶³ Cf. Lamdan, Sarah: When Westlaw Fuels ICE Surveillance. Legal Ethics in the Era of Big Data Policing, N.Y.U. Review of Law & Social Change 43 (2), 2019, S. 255–293. <https://socialchangenyu.com/review/when-westlaw-fuels-ice-surveillance-legal-ethics-in-the-era-of-big-data-policing/> and also: Librarianship at the Crossroads of ICE Surveillance, In the library with the lead pipe 13.11.2019, <https://www.inthelibrarywiththeleadpipe.org/2019/ice-surveillance/>

⁶⁴ Cf. Jung, Justin: UCLA School of Law holds contracts with companies selling personal data to ICE, Daily Bruin 17.07.2020, <https://dailybruin.com/2020/07/17/ucla-school-of-law-holds-contracts-with-companies-selling-personal-data-to-ice>

⁶⁵ Swauger, Shea: Some of my co-workers, Twitter, @SheaSwauger, 13.12.2019, <https://twitter.com/SheaSwauger/status/1205587676172144641>

⁶⁶ Cf. Chafkin, Max: Peter Thiel. München 2021, S. 278f.

5. Statements

Currently, the AWBI statement is still the authoritative statement on the topic. The aim of the information paper is „to encourage a broad debate within the academic community – at the level of academic decision-makers, among academics, and within information infrastructure institutions – so as to reflect on the practice of tracking, its legality, the measures required for compliance with data protection and the consequences of the aggregation of usage data, thereby enabling such measures to be adopted.“⁶⁷

This motivation was taken up by the RfII (Council for Information Infrastructures) in its current recommendation paper on data services with the announcement that, if necessary, it would „take a position on the use and consequences of corresponding technologies in the research process at a later point in time.“⁶⁸ Learned societies⁶⁹ and university associations⁷⁰ have already done so, and scientists are also expressing their views in many cases, be it individually, be it in the initiatives »Stop Tracking Science!«⁷¹ and »Take action to stop the lock up of research and learning«.⁷² However, those who have not yet taken a stand in Germany are the library committees and associations - in contrast to the American Library Association, for example, which finds clear words in its »Resolution on the Misuse of Behavioral Data Surveillance in Libraries«.⁷³

6. Conclusions

6.1. Surveillance Capitalism

User tracking on publishing platforms, the development of workbenches, and the expansion of business lines are sample applications of Shoshana Zuboff's analyses of surveillance capitalism⁷⁴ as she defines it at the beginning of her major study:

„Surveillance capitalism unilaterally claims human experience as free raw material for translation into behavioral data. Although some of these data are applied to product or service improvement, the rest are declared as a proprietary *behavioral surplus*, fed into advanced manufacturing processes known as »machine intelligence,« and fabricated into *predictive products* that anticipate what you will do now, soon, and later. Finally, these prediction products are traded in a new kind of marketplace for behavioral predictions, that I call *behavioral futures market*. Surveillance capitalists have grown

⁶⁷ DFG 2021, p. 14.

⁶⁸ RfII: Nutzung und Verwertung von Daten im wissenschaftlichen Raum. Empfehlungen zur Ausgestaltung von Dateninstanzen an der Schnittstelle zwischen Wissenschaft und Wirtschaft. Göttingen 2021, p. 15.

<https://rfii.de/download/nutzung-und-verwertung-von-daten-im-wissenschaftlichen-raum-september-2021/>

⁶⁹ Cf. DGPs-Vorstand und Kommission Open Science unterstützen »Stop Tracking Science«-Initiative, 7.12.2021, <https://www.dgps.de/aktuelles/details/dgps-vorstand-und-kommission-open-science-unterstuetzen-stop-tracking-science-initiative/> and: DPG-Positionspapier zur Zukunft des wissenschaftlichen Publikationswesens, 13.11.2021, <https://www.dpg-physik.de/veroeffentlichungen/publikationen/stellungnahmen-der-dpg/wissenschaftssystem/dpg-positionspapier-zur-zukunft-des-wissenschaftlichen-publikationswesens>

⁷⁰ Cf. LERU Data Statement, <https://www.leru.org/publications/is-university-autonomy-threatened-by-eu-data-policy-and-law>

⁷¹ <https://stoptrackingscience.eu/>

⁷² <https://investinopen.org/blog/take-action-to-stop-the-lock-up-of-research-and-learning/>

⁷³ Resolution on the Misuse of Behavioral Data Surveillance in Libraries, 26.1.2021,

<https://www.ala.org/advocacy/intfreedom/datasurveillanceresolution>. Andreas Degkwitz as chairman of the DBV expressed himself in a comparable way on a panel discussion of Wikimedia Deutschland, see the recording on <https://av.tib.eu/media/55690>

⁷⁴ Cf. Pooley, Jefferson D.: Surveillance Publishing. Working Paper 16.11.2021,

<https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv/j6ung/download> and the elaborated version on the blog »Elephant in the lab«, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6384605>

immensely wealthy from this trading operations, for many companies are eager to lay bets on our future behavior.⁷⁵

The starting point of this development was when Google's engineers realized early on that the collateral data generated in vast quantities by search queries could be used to „turn the search engine into a recursive learning system[.]“⁷⁶ This became the starting point for Adwords, which Google used to survive the dot-com crisis and begin to drive profitability to dizzying heights. In the process, data extraction became an imperative for action, because missing data meant unpredictable behavior, and this meant lost revenue. Google's diversification from the search engine to a wide range of services and even operating systems and hardware has its starting point here and was the model for the other platforms of the GAFAM complex of the large Internet corporations Google, Apple, Facebook, Amazon and Microsoft as well as many smaller companies, e.g. in the ad tech sector. They all turn prediction products into behavior modification as a final step. The barely perceptible »nudging« of user behavior in the desired direction, with which the map app then adapts the driving route to consumer habits, the recommendations that just happen to be appropriate at that moment - all these predictive products from immense proprietary databases that soon know the individual better than they know themselves are summarized succinctly by one of Zuboff's many interviewees: „We are learning how to write the music, and then we let the music make them dance.“⁷⁷

The corollary of this is that the move towards a data analytics business model, as seen in the major publishers, and which has led to intensive collaboration with the major players in surveillance capitalism, is a fundamental decision in favor of a specific paradigm that foregrounds its rules of the game and operates only according to them. This is not something that can be negotiated in detail and defined in guidelines, contracts or general terms and conditions according to customers' wishes, because this paradigm means a fundamental asymmetry of knowledge, possibility of action and power. For Zuboff, insisting on privacy protection vis-à-vis these players is therefore comparable to „asking Henry Ford to make each Model T by hand or asking a giraffe to shorten its neck. Such demands are existential threats. They violate the basic mechanisms and laws of motion that produce this market leviathan's concentration of knowledge, power and wealth.“⁷⁸

6.2. There are no free lunches (and no quick fixes)

We see a significant part of the principles of surveillance capitalism at work in current information infrastructures, but so far reflect little on this. What nudging is already at work, be it through misunderstood recommender systems, be it through other measures - we don't know and therefore, like Zuboff, „have returned to the essential questions that define the division of learning: *Who knows? Who decides? Who decides who decides?*“⁷⁹ For this reason, we must also be skeptical of those voices that could in principle be in favor of science analytics if it were implemented in accordance with data protection laws.⁸⁰ The spoon needed to eat out of the same pot as the devil, as the saying goes, cannot be that long.

Such considerations are also questionable because they implicitly presuppose that nothing will change in the repertoire of forms of science communication at its core and that 21st century science will continue to be locked into 17th century media forms. It is obvious that this can hardly be

⁷⁵ Zuboff, Shoshana: *The age of surveillance capitalism*. London 2019, p. 8.

⁷⁶ Zuboff 2019, p. 68.

⁷⁷ Zuboff 2019, p. 294.

⁷⁸ Zuboff 2019, p. 191.

⁷⁹ Zuboff 2019, p. 326.

⁸⁰ Cf. Wissenschaftsrat: *Empfehlungen zur Transformation des wissenschaftlichen Publizierens zu Open Access*. Bonn 2022, p. 48. <https://www.wissenschaftsrat.de/download/2022/9477-22.html>

productive, at least for the growing number of data-intensive disciplines. For them, research under such circumstances becomes more and more like when a software developer writes his code, then publishes a paper about it, and the next developer tries to guess the source code from it, and then adds to it. Which is more purposeful: such an approach or Git?⁸¹

We thus see in the current publication infrastructures a corruption and perversion of the increasingly past written culture for exploitation purposes. As explained at the outset, the digital transformation is giving rise to new forms of reading and writing that must be able to develop their own understanding of good practice - but in the field of scholarly communication, this has so far taken place only in homeopathic doses for the benefit of established power relations. Yet the alternatives are at the starting line: there is Open Research Europe, there are detailed proposals to replace traditional journals with decentralized structures based on open interfaces.⁸² This would also allow the digital added values to be much better leveraged through the data markets currently emerging, such as the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), without exposing them to external interests in the same way that publications already are.

Thus, an exit from user tracking is not a matter of turning adjusting screws, but a paradigm shift. What is needed for all parts of the research life cycle is an effort comparable to the one we are currently undertaking for research data with the NFDI and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This is costly and cannot be accomplished with a few procedural changes. It is certainly also a financial effort at first - as are all efforts in the context of digital sovereignty. However, given the high expenses associated with the current system, this should not be a stumbling block. As always, it is only up to the first step.

To motivate this, here's another quick comparison: when Edward Snowden went public in 2013, a surprised public was treated to a glimpse of how the world had changed since September 11, 2001. Intelligence agencies that scanned the entire Internet, cracked the encryption of Blackberries, and intercepted shipments from network equipment maker Cisco to build backdoors into hardware - that had never been seen before. A lot has happened since Snowden's whistleblowing, but more to the comfort of the Five Eyes, the intelligence alliance of Australia, New Zealand, the United States, Canada and the United Kingdom. Surveillance advertising has become so ubiquitous that the services no longer have to do much of it themselves: they don't have to break in, they don't have to get questionable legal titles from secret courts - they go data shopping and buy the things they want to know through the official channels. Localization data alone is a market worth billions, and not just in relation to mobile devices, but also, for example, in relation to automobiles. The company Ulysses advertises that it can locate every vehicle on earth in real time, except in North Korea and Cuba. Since the company also sells to the military, everyone who gets into his or her car is now a potential target.⁸³

The scientific community had already experienced the destructive power of data attacks several years before Snowden: In November 2009, the University of East Anglia's Climate Research Centre was the victim of a carefully prepared hacker attack in which mails and documents were stolen. The material was then arranged, edited, and selectively quoted on the web in order to portray climate researchers as part of a conspiracy and as frauds. What climate change deniers called »Climategate« took its course with years of fierce political and legal battles and, not least, personal

⁸¹ Cf. Siems, Renke: When your journal reads you. User tracking on science publisher platforms. Elephant in the Lab, 14.04.2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4683778>

⁸² Cf. Brembs, Björn et.al.: Replacing academic journals, Zenodo 24.09.2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5526635>

⁸³ Cf. Cox, Joseph: Cars have your Location. This Spy Firm wants to sell It to the U.S. Military, Vice 17.03.2021, <https://www.vice.com/en/article/k7adn9/car-location-data-telematics-us-military-ulysses-group>

threats. Action against climate change was delayed and accusations continued to circulate on the web and in the media, despite all refutations.⁸⁴

Since then, scientists have been repeatedly and increasingly exposed to attacks, currently in the context of the pandemic.⁸⁵ At the same time, more and more data about everyone is available through user tracking, which can be instrumentalized: From the combination of information behavior, data traces in commercial research tools, and online biographies as a whole, any exposure can be derived and any targeted attack can be ammunitionized. Those who translate the abbreviation SaaS as »Surveillance as a Service« (actually: Software as a Service) can perhaps save themselves the trouble of breaking into the data center in the future. This means that what Snowden currently wrote about the major Internet companies will apply:

„It is crucial to bear in mind that the industry’s problem is not data »protection,« it is data COLLECTION. Mass surveillance must be recognized as a crime, not a business model.“⁸⁶

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⁸⁴ Cf. McKie, Robin: Climategate 10 years on. What lessons have we learned? The Guardian, 09.11.2019, <https://www.theguardian.com/theobserver/2019/nov/09/climategate-10-years-on-what-lessons-have-we-learned>

⁸⁵ Cf. Nogrady, Bianca: 'I hope you die'. How the COVID pandemic unleashed attacks on scientists, Nature 13.10.2021, <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-021-02741-x>

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